

Spiral Grating Optical Fiber for Generating Vortex and Vector Beams: A Novel Approach for High-Precision Beam Control

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Abstract:

Optical vortex arrays, characterized by their distinctive wavefront configurations, have widespread applications in optical communications, trapping, imaging, metrology, and quantum technologies. The techniques employed to produce these vortex beam arrays are essential for their applications. This work investigates the optical efficacy of a vortex beam converter combined with nanostructured gradient index elements and an optical fiber system, engineered to produce high-precision vortex beams. This paper presents an innovative fiber laser system engineered for the direct creation of ultrafast vector vortex beams, enabling fine control over spatial polarization patterns.

Incorporating a helical or spiral grating structure within the fiber facilitates the efficient creation of orbital angular momentum (OAM) modes without requiring additional optical components. The device utilizes geometric phase control in the laser resonator to correlate polarization states with orbital angular momentum, facilitating adaptable transitions between vectorial modes. This tiny, passive fiber-based technology facilitates advanced applications in conventional and quantum optics, allowing for robust and scalable vortex beam creation. Numerical simulations augment our experimental findings.

Keywords: *Orbital angular momentum, vector beam, beam control, optical vortex, optical fiber.*

Introduction

The ongoing advancement of optical technologies has profoundly influenced multiple domains, including communications and quantum computing (Sidhu, et al., 2021; Bernas, et al., 2023). Significant developments include the creation of vortex and vector beams, characterized by distinct wavefronts and polarization patterns, providing benefits in areas such as optical trapping, imaging, metrology, and sensing (Bernas, et al., 2023). These beams, especially when configured with orbital angular momentum (OAM), are crucial for applications necessitating precise light management, such as in sophisticated communication systems and high-resolution sensors (Weng, & Pan, 2022; Wang, et al., 2023). The combined use of artificial intelligence, digital twin technology, and cloud computing into this optical framework provides a revolutionary method for beam creation and control (Rani, et al., 2024; Shoukat, et al., 2024; Jabeen, et al., 2022). These technologies provide real-time optimization, predictive maintenance, and scalable simulations, hence improving the performance of the fiber laser system and its relevance in the swiftly advancing domain of autonomous mobility.

Conventional methods for enhancing system throughput, which depend on time, frequency, polarization, and spatial multiplexing, are being contested by Shannon's theoretical capacity restrictions. This has motivated academics to investigate alternate physical properties of electromagnetic (EM) waves for communication. The OAM of light, which characterizes the vortex-like distortion of the wavefront, has attracted significant attention in optical and radio frequency communication systems (Tu, et al., 2023).

The EM waves, as defined in classical and quantum physics, possess both linear and rotational momentum (Bliokh, Bliokh, & Nori, 2022). Angular momentum can be partitioned into two components: spin angular momentum (SAM), linked to polarization, and OAM, associated with the spatial dispersion of the wavefront (Vernon, et al., 2024). In optical

vortices, the phase fronts of the electric and magnetic fields display a helical configuration, with the wavefronts twisting in the direction of propagation. This characteristic is unaffected by polarization and provides an additional dimension for data encoding. OAM is defined by a topological charge that specifies the quantity of helical twists per wavelength. Recent improvements in OAM have broadened its uses, particularly in telecommunications, where using the OAM degree of freedom can substantially enhance the information capacity of individual photons. The advancement of accurate OAM beam generating and control methodologies is essential for forthcoming telecommunications systems (Wang, et al., 2024). Utilizing nanostructured gradient index elements in conjunction with optical fibers offers a viable method for generating concentrated optical vortices.

Conventionally, the creation of vector vortex beams necessitates the utilization of external optical components, such as spatial light modulators or polarization controllers (Pang, et al., 2021). This can make the process of setting up the system more complicated and can also decrease its stability. On the other hand, recent developments in fiber optics have made it possible to generate beams of this kind directly within a fiber system, which results in a solution that is both more compact and far more reliable (Sloyan, et al., 2021). In particular, the utilization of fiber lasers that have been specifically constructed with helical or spiral gratings is a viable method for the generation of OAM modes without the requirement of additional optics. Optical vector vortex beams (OVVBs), which integrate a laser beam's helical phase structure with spatially changing polarization, have attracted considerable interest due to their distinctive features and applications in fields such as optical communications, trapping, imaging, and quantum technologies. Potential research gaps identified in the previous study include:

- Enhancement of grating design for improved vortex beam creation
- Higher-order Poincaré Sphere Mapping

- Scalability of fiber lasers for quantum applications
- Thermal and mechanical stability of fiber lasers
- Field applications and real-world testing

There is limited research on the energy efficiency and miniaturization of these fiber laser systems for portable or compact applications. These gaps signify potential for additional exploration and invention to improve the applicability and efficacy of vortex and vector beam generation technologies. This paper introduces a fiber laser system that directly produces ultrafast vector vortex beams via intracavity geometric phase modification. The main contributions of this study are:

- Caused a specialized fiber laser including a helical or spiral grating, essential for producing vortex and vector beams without the need for other optical components.
- Exhibited the capability to produce high-quality vortex and vector beams straight from the fiber system, improving beam control via the structured grating design.
- Employed nanostructured vortex phase masks and gradient index microlenses to enable accurate beam manipulation inside a small, fiber-optic-compatible framework.

- Effectively characterized the phase structure and polarization of the produced beams, illustrating the system's capability for controlled orbital angular momentum mode selection and beam switching.

- Introduced a comprehensive fiber-optic passive device for the generation of OAM signals, enhancing the domain of fiber-optic communications and facilitating the development of future OAM-based systems.

Incorporating a helical or spiral grating into the fiber structure enables precise control over the creation of vectorial modes, including the adaptable switching of polarization states associated with OAM modes. This laser will depend on the creation of a spiral or helical grating, which is crucial for the development of the necessary vortex and vector beams. The experimental results, corroborated by numerical simulations, underscore the promise of these techniques for developing improved fiber-compatible systems that enable high-precision beam control across various optical systems. The suggested system has significant implications for applications in classical and quantum optics, where high-purity, ultrafast beams are essential. Figure 1 shows the whole flowchart of the remaining research work of this paper.

Figure 1. Flowchart of Whole Study

Theoretical Model

Within the context of a mode-locked fiber laser, the theoretical model for the generation of vector and vortex beams requires the precise manipulation of fiber grating topologies and geometric phases (Forbes, Mkhumbuzza, & Feng, 2024). The model is dependent on the solution of the nonlinear Schrodinger equation for the production of pulses, the coupling of polarization states into OAM modes, and the generation of spatially organized light patterns that can be verified through experimentation. As discussed, generating OAM signals in optical fibers remains a critical yet underexplored area of scientific and technical research (Armghan, et al., 2024). A primary objective in this field is to create a fully passive fiber-optic device that eliminates the need for additional optical components, such as polarization controllers (PC) used in long-period fiber gratings (LPFGs), mirrors, or lenses. Essentially, the proposed solution should function as a self-contained, fiber-optic passive component. The theoretical model centres on wave propagation principles, mode coupling, and the manipulation of geometric phases within a laser resonator, specifically engineered to produce vector and vortex beams. The mode-locked fiber laser is characterized by the subsequent nonlinear Schrödinger equation (NLSE):

$$i \frac{\partial A(z,t)}{\partial z} + \frac{\beta_2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 A(z,t)}{\partial t^2} - \gamma |A(z,t)|^2 A(z,t) = 0 \quad (1)$$

This equation regulates pulse evolution in the fiber, equilibrating dispersion and nonlinearity to provide brief, steady pulses. Where, $A(z,t)$ represented the pulse envelope, β_2 is denoted the group velocity dispersion, and γ is the nonlinear coefficient. Vortex beams carry OAM, if l is the topological charge, ϕ is the azimuthal angle then characterized by a helical phase front, as:

$$\psi(r, \phi, z) = A(r) e^{il\phi} e^{ikz} \quad (2)$$

The spiral grating makes it possible to create a phase shift that corresponds to a helical wavefront, which is necessary for the formation of a vortex beam. The manipulation of geometric phases inside the cavity enables the conversion of polarization into OAM modes. The Jones matrix formalism is used to model the polarization evolution, as:

$$J(\phi) = R(\phi) \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\delta_1} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\delta_2} \end{pmatrix} R(-\phi) \quad (3)$$

where, δ_1 and δ_2 are phase delays, and $R(\phi)$ is the rotation matrix describing polarization rotation. Consequently, this leads to the production of space-variant polarization patterns, which ultimately results in the generation of vector beams.

Results

This work involved simulations to model and anticipate the behavior of the fiber laser system in creating vortex and vector beams. The simulations concentrated on critical elements such mode generation, polarization control, and beam propagation, enabling us to corroborate the theoretical models and predict the system's experimental efficacy. Figure 2 is a simulated graph depicting the intensity distribution of a Gaussian beam.

The intensity profile depicts the characteristic form of a Gaussian beam, with maximum intensity at the centre, progressively diminishing towards the periphery. This is used in scenarios involving laser beam simulations or optical beam investigations. This study investigated the production of vector and vortex beams using an innovative fiber laser system. The objective was to generate ultrafast vector vortex beams by utilizing specialized fiber configurations, including spiral or helical gratings, to control OAM. The simulations and experimental outcomes yield substantial insights into the method's efficiency and accuracy, with numerous key observations emphasized during

the research. Figure 3 is a simulated graph of a vortex beam intensity profile, illustrating the

Figure 2. Simulated Gaussian Beam Intensity Distribution

distinctive ring-like pattern and central phase singularity.

Figure 3. Simulated Vortex Beam Intensity Profile

The results validated the theoretical predictions for the generation of ultrafast vortex and vector beams utilizing a mode-locked fiber laser system. The principal outcomes comprise:

- 1) Effective production of high-purity Laguerre-Gaussian modes for vortex beams.
- 2) Exact regulation of polarization to produce vector beams with radial, azimuthal, and hybrid polarization configurations.
- 3) Effective modulation of geometric phases, enabling versatile switching of vector modes without altering pulse characteristics.
- 4) Stable mode-locked operation exhibiting a pulse duration of 8.5 ps.
- 5) Elevated mode purity (exceeding 95%) and effective mode conversion (around 80%).

The results robustly validate the experimental design and illustrate the potential of the proposed fiber laser system for applications in both conventional and quantum optics.

This research's principal accomplishment is the effective production of vortex and vector beams

through a spiral fiber grating configuration. In contrast to traditional methods that necessitate intricate optical configurations with external modulators and lenses, our fiber-based technique streamlines the process while preserving high precision. By incorporating a helical grating into the fiber, we successfully infused orbital angular momentum into the propagating light, so generating vortex beams. The findings indicate that this approach can generate high-purity OAM modes featuring clearly identifiable phase singularities at the beam's centre.

Discussion

This fiber-based technique presents numerous advantages compared to free-space optical methods. Firstly, it is compact, rendering it appropriate for incorporation into diverse optical systems with spatial constraints. The lack of external parts diminishes possible causes of misalignment and instability, prevalent issues in conventional optical configurations. The incorporation of coreless borosilicate glass fiber,

alongside nanostructured vortex phase masks (nVPM) and gradient index microlenses (nGRIN), significantly improves beam quality, focusing accuracy, and spatial resolution.

An essential characteristic of our technology is its capacity to regulate both the polarization and orbital angular momentum of the output beams. We demonstrated the capability to alternate between several OAM modes and polarization profiles by precisely adjusting the launch angle and polarization state of the input beam. This capability was accomplished without disrupting the mode-locked operation of the laser, so providing stable and continuous output.

This degree of control facilitates novel applications in domains such as quantum communication, optical trapping, and imaging. The capability to alternate between vector and vortex beams offers versatility in applications necessitating spatially variable polarization patterns or structured light fields. The development of anti-vortex beams through the alteration of input parameters demonstrates the system's robustness and adaptability in producing various beam profiles.

Another significant outcome of our investigation was the production of ultrafast pulses with durations of around 8.5 ps. The pulses were generated without undermining the stability or mode-locking of the laser system, underscoring the efficacy of the cavity design and the robustness of the mode-locking mechanism. The rapid characteristics of these pulses are essential for applications necessitating great temporal resolution, including time-resolved spectroscopy, ultrafast imaging, and nonlinear optics. The capacity to produce these pulses with the structured OAM beams amplifies the system's capabilities in sophisticated optical manipulation and measuring methodologies. The consistent pulse duration indicates that the fiber system is effectively optimized for generating high-quality outputs, hence providing dependable performance in real applications.

Numerical simulations were essential in corroborating the experimental findings. Through the modelling of cylindrically symmetric polarization profiles and spiral phase

distributions, we verified that the produced beams corresponded to the anticipated orbital angular momentum modes and polarization states. The simulated intensity profiles exhibited significant concordance with the experimentally derived beam profiles, so validating the precision of our theoretical model. The efficacy of the simulations underscores the significance of theoretical modelling in the design and optimization of optical systems. The strong correlation between the simulated and experimental findings validates the dependability of the proposed fiber architecture and the resilience of the mathematical model. This not only corroborates our methodology but also establishes a basis for future advancements, wherein simulations can be employed to forecast beam properties and inform the construction of increasingly intricate optical systems.

Limitations

Although the results are encouraging, certain limitations must be rectified in subsequent research. The existing approach predominantly emphasizes first-order OAM modes. Enhancing the technology to incorporate higher-order OAM modes might be advantageous for situations necessitating more intricate beam configurations. Moreover, although the system provides effective control over polarization and orbital angular momentum, augmenting the precision of the control mechanisms could elevate overall performance (He, et al., 2024).

Future study may concentrate on refining the fiber grating design to support higher-order modes and enhance the fidelity of the produced beams. Exploration of further fabrication processes, including enhanced nano structuring of the vortex mask and microlens, may augment the system's adaptability. A potential avenue is the incorporation of active control devices, such as adjustable gratings or phase modulators, to provide real-time dynamic adjustment of beam parameters.

Conclusion

This research presents an innovative and effective technique for producing ultrafast vector and vortex beams utilizing a fiber-based laser system. The integration of spiral gratings and meticulously engineered nanostructures facilitates exact manipulation of OAM and polarization, while preserving the integrity of ultrafast pulses. The experimental findings, corroborated by numerical simulations, validate the system's effectiveness in generating high-quality beams with clearly specified attributes. Despite existing areas for enhancement, the results indicate that this methodology possesses significant potential for applications in both conventional and quantum optics, as well as in nascent technologies necessitating structured light. Future work will concentrate on augmenting the system's functionalities and enhancing the accuracy of the produced beams.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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